

Tomb of Sunan Gresik

also known as "Tomb of Syekh Maulana Malik Ibrahim, Gresik"

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Entry tags: Tomb, Islamic Traditions, Religious Group, Sufi, Religious Place

Since the nineteenth century, Syekh Maulana Malik Ibrahim (1359-1419), known variously as Syeik Maghribi, Sunan Gresik or Syek Ibrahim as-Samarkandi is regarded as the first among the Wali Songo. The Wali Songo refers to the nine Sufi saints who introduced Islam to Java during the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries (Sunyoto 2017). The discovery of the fifteenth century tombstone of Syekh Maulana Malik Ibrahim during the nineteenth century, elevated him to the status of Wali Songo. Babad Diponegoro was the first Javanese Babad to include Maulana Malik Ibrahim within the category of Wali Songo. Syekh Siti Jenar is sometimes included in the category of Wali Songo but sometimes his historical existence is denied due to controversy as he was the only pantheist among the Sufi saints of Java (Gil 2014). Each of the Wali Songo has a recognized tomb attached to a mosque and is a site for local pilgrimage or ziarah. Pilgrim visits occur at specific times, dictated by intersections of cycles of the Javanese calendar. Each saint of the Wali Songo is related to other members of the council either through genealogy or the master-apprentice relationship. Sunan Gresik was born in Samarkand (now in Uzbekistan) in 1359. By the time he was twenty, he was trained as a physician (Nourse 2013). Timur Lang's bullying tactics contributed to his migration to the Champa Kingdom (a collection of kingdoms that controlled parts of the coast of modern day Vietnam). At Vijaya, the then capital of the Champa kingdom, he succeeded in curing the king's illness. The King of Champa offered his daughter in marriage as a reward for Sunan Gresik's cure. Legend states that the Champa King subsequently converted to Islam (Nourse 2013). In 1404, Sunan Gresik and his Champa wife sailed to the north coast of Java and settled near the Gresik harbor. Sunan Gresik's son from his Champa wife was Raden Rahmat, popularly known as Sunan Ampel according to Babad Ngampeldenta (Sunyoto 2017). In Java, Sunan Gresik's medical skills led to his sanctification as Wali Gresik. His skills as a physician attracted followers from the inland Hindu-Buddhist kingdom of Majapahit. As with most Islamic physicians of his time, Sunan Gresik belonged to a secret Sufi brotherhood Kubrawiyya Tariqa (Nourse 2013). The Kubrawiyya Tariqa was led by Syaikh Jumadil Kubra. Kubra taught that one could perceive Allah's healing essence as a glowing light (Nourse 2013). Over several generations, Sunan Gresik's descendants positioned themselves through strategic marriages with Javanese nobility and centralized power through control over sacred mystical knowledge (Nourse 2013). Dutch scholar J.P. Moquette notes from Sunan Gresik's tomb stone marker with an Arabic inscription that states [translated into English] : " This is the grave of Maulana Malik Ibrahim who passed away on Monday, 12 Rabi'ul Awwal, 812 Hijrah [date corresponding with April 7, 1419 of the Gregorian Calendar]. Exalted teacher of the princes and friend of the poor and destitute, he sacrificed his life for the cause of Islam. Maulana Malik Ibrahim, is originally from Kashan [Persia]. May Allah shower His mercy and grant him a place in paradise." The tomb of Sunan Gresik is situated less than 200 meters from the Gresik town square in the area of Desa Gapura. Sheltered by a Pendopo (Javanese Pandhapa), the tomb of Sunan Gresik reflects the imprint of Javanese architecture. The Pendopo is a large pavilion-like structure supported by columns and is rectangular in plan. It provides shelter to the pilgrims from sun and rain.

Date Range: 1419 CE - 2020 CE

Region: East Java Province

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Indonesia, East Java

The tomb of Sufi saint Maulana Malik Ibrahim alias

Sunan Gresik is located 200 meters from the alun-alun or town hall of Gresik in the city of Gresik, East Java province, Indonesia.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Sylwia Gil, "Syekh Siti Jenar: Javanese Mystic," English Version of the Conference Article "Odcienie Indonezji," red. Renata Lesner-Szwarc, Oficyna Wydawnicza Kucharski, Torun (Poland), 2014

– Source 1: George Quinn, "Throwing Money at the Holy Door: Commercial Aspects of Popular Pilgrimage in Java," in *Expressing Islam: Religious Life and Politics in Indonesia*, edited by Greg Fealy and Sally White (Singapore: ISEAS, 2008).

Notes: George Quinn's chapter highlights the reasons for undertaking ziarah (pious visitation) to the shrines of the Wali Songo.

– Source 1: Solichin Salam, *Sekitar Wali Sanga* (Kudus: Menara Kudus, 1960).

– Source 1: Azyumardi Azra, *Islam in the Indonesian World: An Account of Institutional Formation* (Bandung: Mizan, 2006).

– Source 2: Agus Sunyoto, *Atlas Wali Songo: Buku Pertama yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah* (Bandung: Mizan, 2017).

– Source 3: Jennifer Nourse, "The Meaning of Dukun and Allure of Sufi Healers: How Persian Cosmopolitans Transformed Malay-Indonesian History," *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies* 44, no. 3 (2013): 400–422.

Notes: Azyumardi Azra provides a nuanced historiographical account for the early history of Islam in the Indonesian archipelago. Agus Sunyoto's *Atlas Wali Songo* is a richly illustrated and empirical account in Bahasa Indonesia of the early history of Islam in Java, prior to the arrival of Maulana Malik Ibrahim. The Atlas also portrays confusing narratives of Babad Jawi that make it problematic for historians specializing in the early history of Islam in the Malay world to accurately trace the genealogies of Wali Songo. For e.g. Syekh Ibrahim Samarkandi is depicted as the father of Sunan Ampel but historians are uncertain whether Syekh Ibrahim Samarkandi refers to Sunan Gresik or whether they are different individuals. Syekh Ibrahim Samarkandi's tomb is situated in Tuban and not Gresik.

– Source 1: Elizabeth Lambourn, "From Cambay to Samudera-Pasai: Export of Gujarati Grave Memorials to Sumatra and Java in the Fifteenth Century C.E.," *Indonesia and the Malay World* 31, no. 90 (2003): 221–89.

Notes: A fine-grained analysis of the similarity in architectural styles between the gravestones at Cambay, on one hand and the gravestones at Gresik, on the other.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://archive.org/details/BabadTanahDjawi/page/n5/mode/2up>

– Source 1 Description: Babad Tanah Jawi, Versi J.J Meinsma, 1874: Edisi Prosa Bahasa Jawa (Muntilan, 1925).

Notes: This copy of Babad Tanah Jawi, sourced from the Internet Archive [Javanese language and Romanized script] highlights two aspects: (a) the early history of Islam in the Indies archipelago (including the downfall of the Majapahit empire by the sixteenth century); and, (b) a brief reference to the life of Maulana Malik Ibrahim although he is not represented in this version as one of the members of the Wali Songo. The chronicle speculates on the Persian ancestry of Maulana Malik Ibrahim.

– Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Serat_Babad_Tanah_Jawi_Jil_1.pdf

– Source 1 Description: Raden Pandji Djojosebroto, Serat Babad Tanah Jawi (Semarang: GCT Van and Co., 1917).

– Source 2 URL: <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP061-2-54#?c=0&m=0&s=0&cv=8&xywh=868%2C0%2C3861%2C2480>

– Source 2 Description: Babad Tanah Jawa versi Drajad [The History of Java version Drajat], British Library, EAP061/2/54, <https://eap.bl.uk/archive-file/EAP061-2-54>

Notes: Raden Pandji Djojosebroto's version of the Babad Tanah Jawi [composed in the Javanese script] and Babad Tanah Jawa versi Drajad [composed in the Jawi script] attribute the Islamization of Java to the Wali Songo. With respect to evaluating the credibility of various Babad texts as historical sources, historians need to pay attention to the fact that the names of Wali Songo and their genealogies vary across the texts such that a perfect harmonization between one Babad text and the other is not possible.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: Scientifically restored ~ 1912 by Rinkes. KITLV Shelfmark 106743

Years of excavation:

– Year range: ~1891-1912

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Unknown

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Other [specify]: A well, believed to have therapeutic properties is situated within a distance of 4 meters from the tomb of Sunan Gresik.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Field doesn't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– I don't know

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Tomb of Maulana Malik Ibrahim. A well, believed to have been sanctified by Maulana Malik Ibrahim and possessing therapeutic properties is located within the tomb complex. The tomb complex also contains the graves of Syech Maulana Ishaq, the father of Sunan Giri and brother of Maulana Malik Ibrahim and also the first Bupati (District Head) of

Gresik, named Poesponegoro. The grave of Poesponegoro dates back to the nineteenth century.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Healing

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– I don't know

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: The demise of Sunan Gresik and his legacy in spreading Islam across Java.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– I don't know

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Imported marble

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Tombstone sculpted out of marble in Cambay, Gujarat.

Notes: The gravestone is made of imported marble and bears striking resemblance to the gravestones found in the Samudera Pasai Sultanate (roughly corresponding with the north coast of Sumatra) and Cambay, Gujarat, as noted by Moquette (see for e.g. Azra 2006). From these observations, Moquette infers that gravestones from Gujarat were produced not only for the local markets but also for Sumatra and Java. By taking gravestones from Gujarat, Malay-Indonesians took Islam from there (Azra 2006). But Indonesian historian Azyumardi Azra (2006) refutes the hypothesis that Islam was carried to Indonesia from Gujarat. He notes that during the Islamization of Pasai (~1297), Gujarat was still a Hindu kingdom.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– I don't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Maulana Malik Ibrahim's headstone has one of the most legible epitaphs of all the Cambay group gravestones in Indonesia. The following inscription on the headstone: "Mufakhr al-Umara' wa 'Umdat al-Salatin wa al-Wuzara' Muhibb al-Masakin wa al-Fuqara' al-shahid al-sa'id Burhan al Dawlah wa al-Din Malik Ibrahim," translated from Arabic as Pride of Nobles and Support of Sultans and Viziers, Friend of the Poor and the Needy, the blessed martyr, Proof of the World and Religion." Grandiloquent titles of this type are seen in the port cities of the Indian Ocean littoral, including the Indies archipelago, from the tenth century onwards. The absence of a line of descent or nasab (i.e. Malik Ibrahim ibn/son of so and so) is also noticeable, perhaps suggesting that he was a first generation convert. For details see Lambourn (2003).

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Maulana Malik Ibrahim's arched headstone fronts a large rectangular cenotaph with ornately carved flat lid and is finished at the other end by a plain arched footstone.

Notes: For details refer Lambourn (2003).

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– I don't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– I don't know

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Field does not know.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: For details regarding the Javanese-Islamic notion of kingship, refer Bernard Arps, "The Power of the Heart that Blazes in the World," *Indonesia and the Malay World* (2019): 1-27, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13639811.2019.1654217>.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– I don't know

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Not applicable.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings are customary at the shrine of Sunan Gresik. Pilgrims undertake a vow (nadar) to repay the saint if their wish is granted.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Flowers and flower petals, perfumed oil and envelopes are sold outside the burial chamber of most popular pilgrimage sites, including Gresik.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: Customary.

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Juru kunci or the tomb custodian.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– I don't know

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Under Indonesia's decentralization laws, the Gresik district administration is empowered to levy taxes on pilgrims.

Notes: Rp 10,000 levied by the Transport Infrastructure Service (Dinas Perhubungan) of the Gresik district government, and Rp 8,000 levied by the village of Gapuro Sukolilo where the tomb is located. For details refer Quinn (2008).

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Ziarah (pilgrim visitation to the shrine of Sunan Gresik) usually takes place either before or after pilgrims undertake the Hajj pilgrimage.

– optional (common)

Notes: Customary. Many pilgrims go to sacred sites in the hope that they can ngalap berkah, that is, access a personal favor that has a supernatural origin. This favor may take many forms – success in an examination or finding a suitable spouse but the desire for wealth probably predominates. Behind the quest for 'easy money' at such sites lies a deeply held conviction that personal wealth can never wholly be a product of individual enterprise and action, but is always, at least in part, a question of accessing the infinite natural abundance of the supernatural (for details refer Quinn 2008).

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– No

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pilgrimage to Sufi shrines such as Sunan Gresik are a form of ngalap berkah, i.e. access supernatural favors such as success in an examination, finding a suitable spouse or recovery from illness.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– No

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The Gresik district government sponsors the festivities at the shrine of Sunan Gresik.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: Takes place in the town square adjacent to the saint's tomb.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annual celebration commemorating Sunan Gresik's birth.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 1.2 million

Notes: See Quinn (2008).

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Water from the well, situated approximately four meters from the tomb of Sunan Gresik, is believed to have therapeutic properties.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: Juru kunci is the caretaker of the tomb of Sunan Gresik.

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– Yes

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Special training is provided to local farmers at the shrine of Sunan Gresik in modern agricultural practices.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– I don't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No